

ISic3462

I.Sicily inscription 3462

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

excavated 2002 and 5 August 2010 on decumanus maximus, Capo Boeo,
Marsala

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo archeologico
regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644939

Bibliography

Silvestrini, M. 2014. Una nuova attestazione del cursus publicus dalla Sicilia tardoantica. In Demougin, S., Navarro Caballero, M.(eds.), *Se déplacer dans l'Empire romain : approches épigraphiques: XVIIIe rencontre franco-italienne d'épigraphie du monde romain, Bordeaux 7-8 octobre 2011*. Bordeaux. pp.

123-133. At fig.1-4

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